

**SURVEY OF FACTORS CONTRIBUTING TO THE SPREAD OF CHOLERA IN
KATSINA METROPOLIS**

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CHAPTER ONE

1.0 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Study

Cholera is an infection of the small intestine that is caused by the bacterium *Vibrio cholerae* 01 and 0139 (Riyan, 2004). The main symptoms are profuse watery diarrhoea and vomiting. Transmission is primarily through consuming contaminated drinking water or food. The severity of the diarrhoea and vomiting can lead to rapid dehydration and electrolyte imbalance. Every year there is an estimated 3-5 million cholera cases and 100,000-120,000 deaths due to cholera. The short incubation period of two to five days, enhance the potentially explosive pattern of outbreaks (Faruque, 2008).

Cholera transmission is closely linked to inadequate environmental management. Typical at-risk areas include peri-urban slums, where basic infrastructure is not available, as well as camps for internally displaced people or refugees, where minimum requirements of clean water and sanitation are not met. The consequences of a disaster – such as disruption of water and sanitation systems, or the displacement of populations to inadequate and overcrowded camps – can increase the risk of cholera transmission should the bacteria be present or introduced.

Epidemics have never arisen from dead bodies. Cholera remains a global threat to public health and a key indicator of lack of social development. Recently, the re-emergence of cholera has been noted in parallel with the ever-increasing size of vulnerable populations living in unsanitary conditions (Emch 2008). Two serogroups of *v. cholera* - 01 and 0139 - causes outbreaks (Alexander 2008). *v. cholera* 01 causes the majority of the outbreaks, while 0139 - first identified in Bangladesh in 1992 –is confined to South-East Asia. Non-01 and non-0139 *v. cholera* can cause mild diarrhoea but do not generate epidemics. The bacteria are transmitted via contaminated drinking water or food. Pathogenic *v. cholera* can survive refrigeration and

freezing in food supplies (Reidl *et al.*, 2002). The dosage of bacteria required to cause an infection in healthy volunteers via oral administration of living vibrio is greater than 1000 organisms (Hartely, 2006). After consuming an antacid, however, cholera development in most volunteers after consumption of only 100 cholera vibrio experiments also show that vibrio consumed with food are more likely to cause infection than those from water alone (Finkelstein 1996). Cases tend to be clustered by location as well as season, with most infections occurring in children ages 1-5 years (Hartely, 2006).

Cholera is a severe water-borne infectious disease caused by the bacterium *Vibrio cholera*. In 2005, 131,943 cases including 2,272 deaths have notified from 52 countries. The year was marked by a particular significant series of outbreaks in West Africa, which affected 14 countries and accounted for 58% of all cholera cases world-wide. In the same year Nigeria had 4,477 cases and 174 deaths. There was a reported case of cholera in 2008 in Nigeria in which 429 dead out of 6,330 cases. More so, 2,304 cases in Niger State in which 114 were reported death in 2008 (NBS, 2009). Recent years have seen a strong trend of cholera outbreaks in developing countries, including among others, those in India (2007), Iraq (2008), Congo (2008), Zimbabwe (2008-2009), and Haiti (2010).

Cholera is a disease characterized by profuse diarrhoea accompanied by severe dehydration and loss of electrolytes (Colwell and Huq, 2004), caused by toxigenic *Vibrio cholera*, a serologically diverse, environmental, and gram-negative rod bacterium (Li *et al.*, 2002). In the absence of appropriate treatment, there is a high mortality rate. Cholera is a major public health concern because of its high transmissibility, death-to-case ratio and ability to occur in epidemic and pandemic forms (Kaper *et al.*, 2005). Cholera is responsible for an estimated death of 120,000 globally every year (WHO, 2001), and still continues to be a scourge worldwide covering all continents. In developing countries with endemic areas, cholera is still very significant with the incidence of more than five million cases per year (Tauxe *et al.*, 1994; Lan

and Reeves, 2002). The explosive epidemic nature and the severity of the disease and the potential threat to food and water supplies have prompted the listing of V. cholera as an organism of biological defence research (Zhang *et al.*, 2003). In an epidemic, the great majority of cases can be recognized by clinical diagnosis easily and a bacteriological diagnosis is often not required.

Cholera is endemic in Nigeria (Falade and Lawoyin, 2009) and epidemiological features (Hutin *et al.*, 2003) have been reported from various parts of the country with investigations on possible sources of outbreaks. Outbreaks of cholera had been reported from various States in Nigeria such as Ogun, Edo, Pleatue State, Katsina etc., of Nigeria. Investigations on the outbreak of cholera in Nigeria have focused on the epidemiological features, the probable source of contamination and the risk factors without spatial linkage of health data. However, advances in Geographical Information Systems (GIS) technology provides this opportunity and have become an indispensable tool for processing, analyzing and visualizing spatial data within the domains of environmental health, disease ecology and public health (Kistemann *et al.*, 2002). Therefore, this study seeks to assess the factors contributing to the spread of cholera in the Katsina metropolis.

1.2 Statement of Research Problem

Cholera seems to remain a major public health issue and it seems that inadequate knowledge of parents to make adequate provision for clean water, a clean environment and decent toilets contributed to its high prevalence among children in Nigeria, especially in Katsina State.

The researcher observed that many of the victims face a lot of health challenges such as extreme diarrhoea, nausea, vomiting and dehydration. The infected children may lose as much as a litre of fluid an hour, nausea and vomiting may last for several hours at a time and dehydration causes electrolyte imbalance which can lead to muscle spasms and shock. Hence, victims suffer

a life-long disability, reduction in life expectancy and the majority of affected individuals hardly survive to adulthood.

The high morbidity and mortality associated with cholera produce grief and permanent anxiety to the family, pain, frustration and a poor quality of life to the patient, serious financial stress to the family and a large drain on the national health expenditure. (Zhang *et al.*, 2003).

In order to reduce high morbidity and mortality associated with this disease, there is a need to intensify effort towards educating the general populace on the factors contributing to the spread of cholera, causes, symptoms and preventable measure to this epidemic.

1.3 Justification of the study

The threat of cholera rampaging through Nigeria has long been of concern to many. The crowded settings coupled with minimal water, sanitation, hygiene and health services, present a fearsome breeding ground for cholera to quickly escalate beyond control. In an attempt to avoid this worst-case scenario, a massive response needs to be mounted by the Government to enlighten the general public about the factors contributing to this deadly disease and also ways to avoid the outbreak. Hygiene promoters should be employed to work every day, sharing information on how to avoid contracting the illness and the signs and symptoms of the disease.

The research work is important in several ways both to the health personnel and the individual within the society. Firstly, this study will expose to us some of the causes of cholera outbreak in Katsina metropolis and also proffer ways of preventing cholera outbreak within our community, outbreak within the Nigeria economy and also present the figures of cholera victims who dies as a result of this disease, by this information, the government can swing into action by providing various measures in other to limit or prevent further outbreak of the disease

in our community. This research will also be a contribution to the body of literature in the subject area, thereby constituting the empirical literature for future research in the subject area.

1.4 Aims and Objectives

The aim of this study is to assess the factors contributing to the spread of cholera in the Katsina metropolis and isolate *Vibrio cholerae*.

However, the specific objectives of the study are:

- i. To find out the factors contributing to the spread of cholera in the Katsina metropolis.
- ii. To determine the problems associated with the prevention of cholera in the Katsina metropolis.
- iii. To determine the ways of preventing cholera outbreaks in the Katsina metropolis.
- iv. To isolate and identify *Vibrio cholerae* from faecal sample.

1.5 Research Hypothesis

H0: There is no significant effect of poor sanitation, water contamination or food contamination as a factors that contribute to the spread of Cholera in Katsina metropolis.

H1: There is a significant effect of poor sanitation, water contamination or food contamination as a factors that contribute to the spread of Cholera in Katsina metropolis.

1.6 Research Significance

To the researcher: the study was enabling the researcher to have more knowledge, skills and experience about the factors contributing to the spread of cholera. This study also was helping to put into practice the knowledge and skills acquired in research methodology as a course learn in class. The researcher was acquiring the relevant information about dissertation writing in order to become familiar with research activities as a whole.

To the Public: this study will expose to the public some of the factors contributing to the spread of cholera and also proffer ways of preventing cholera outbreak within our community and outbreaks within Nigeria, by this information, the public can swing into action by taking various measures in order to limit or prevent further outbreaks of the disease in our community.

To the future researchers: The data obtained went for future references on the topic by academicians who went studying in the same area of the study.

1.7 Scope of the Study

Conceptually the study hovers around the factors contributing to the spread of cholera in Katsina metropolis and isolation of *Vibrio cholerae*. Extensive investigation is conducted on the techniques or tools used and preference (if any) and why such. However, the research was limited to the Katsina metropolis only due to the schedule of the researchers.

CHAPTER TWO

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 BACKGROUND

Cholera caused by *Vibrio cholera* continues to be a global threat to public health and a key indicator of lack of social development. Once common throughout the world, the infection is now largely confined to developing countries in the tropics and subtropics. It is endemic in Africa, parts of Asia, the Middle East, and South and Central America. In endemic areas, outbreaks usually occur when war or civil unrest disrupts public sanitation services. (Farmer, 2016).

Natural disasters like earthquakes, tsunamis, volcanic eruptions, landslides and floods also contribute to outbreaks by disrupting the normal balance of nature. This creates many health problems, food and water supplies can become contaminated by parasites and- bacteria when essential systems like those for water and sewage are destroyed (Farmer, 2016).

Developing countries are disproportionately affected because of their lack of resources, infrastructure and disaster preparedness systems. In newly affected areas, outbreaks may occur during any season and affect all ages equally. The organism normally lives in aquatic environments along the coast. People acquire its infection by consuming contaminated water, seafood, or other foods. Once infected, they excrete the bacteria in the stool. Thus, the infection can spread rapidly, particularly in areas where human waste is untreated (Farmer, 2016).

In Nigeria, the infection is endemic and outbreaks are not unusual. In the last quarter of 2015, it was speculated that more than 260 people died of cholera in four Northern states with over 96 people in Maiduguri, Biu, Gwoza, Dikwa and Jere council areas of Bauchi state. Most of

the Northern states of Nigeria rely on hand-dug wells and contaminated ponds as a source of drinking water. Usually, the source of the contamination is other cholera patients when their untreated diarrhoea discharge is allowed to get into water supplies (Skogan, 2020).

The 2019 outbreak of cholera and gastroenteritis and the attendant deaths in some regions in Nigeria brought to the forefront the vulnerability of poor communities and most especially children to the infection. The outbreak was attributed to rain which washed sewage into open wells and ponds, where people obtain water for drinking and household needs. The regions ravaged by the scourge include Jigawa, Bauchi, Gombe, Yobe, Borno, Adamawa, Taraba, FCT, Cross River, Kaduna, Osun and Rivers. Even though the epidemic was recorded in these areas, epidemiological evidence indicated that the entire country was at risk, with the postulation that the outbreak was due to hyper-virulent strains of the organism (Skogan, 2020).

In Nigeria, the first series of cholera outbreaks was reported between 1970- 1990. Despite this long experience with cholera, an understanding of the epidemiology of the disease aiding its persistence in outbreak situations is still lacking (Skogan, 2020). This study therefore provides the knowledge gaps of the infection with the hope that it will help to develop targeted approaches to controlling the infection.

2.2 Concept of Cholera

Cholera is an infection of the small intestine caused by the bacterium “*Vibrio cholera*”, resulting in profuse watery diarrhoea. The bacterium named *Vibrio cholera* is known to be the microorganism that causes a deadly disease known as cholera (Ademola, 2011). The first successful isolation of the *Vibrio cholerae* bacterium occurs as an important instance in the history of medicine on the whole. It is rather very tough to a certain who discovered cholera.

The reasons are not far to seek. Most people attribute the discovery of cholera to Robert Koch, the famous German scientist (Ademola, 2011).

Cholera is only one of many types of diarrheal disease, but its global importance is underlined by its inclusion in the WHO Communicable Disease Surveillance and Response (CSR) list. The subsequent loss of fluid volume causes a drop in blood pressure and circulatory shock. If the patient remains untreated, they become progressively weaker, sometimes to the point of death, within 12-24 hours of the onset of symptoms. If the patient survives, then the infection usually lasts 1-5 days (Balakrishna, 2011). The disease is common in places with poor sanitation, crowding, war and famine. Common locations include parts of Africa, South Asia, and Latin America. If you are travelling to one of those areas, knowing the following cholera facts can help protect you and your family (Ademola, 2011).

The primary symptoms of cholera are profuse diarrhoea (Looseness of bowel movement) and vomiting of clear fluid. These symptoms usually start suddenly, half a day to five days after ingestion of the bacteria. The diarrhoea is frequently described as "rice-water" in nature and may have a fishy odour. An untreated person with cholera may produce 10 to 20 litres (3 to 5 US gal) of diarrhoea a day. Severe cholera kills about half of affected individuals. Estimates of the ratio of asymptomatic to symptomatic infections have ranged from 3 to 100. Cholera has been nicknamed the "blue death" because a person's skin may turn bluish-grey from extreme loss of fluids (Balakrishna, 2011).

2.2.1 The Cholera Bacterium and Toxin

Vibrio cholerae is a member of the family Vibrionaceae, which includes three medically important genera of water-dwelling bacteria. It is a short, gram-negative, rod-shaped bacterium

that appears curved when isolated. There are more than 200 different serogroups of *Vibrio cholerae*, which are distinguished based on the structure of a protein called the O antigen in the bacterium's cell wall. Several of these serogroups are pathogenic in humans; however, only two serogroups of *Vibrio cholerae*—O1 and O139 (sometimes called the Bengal serogroup) are known to cause cholera (Balakrishna, 2011).

Pathogenic O1 and O139 *Vibrio cholerae* have the ability to produce cholera toxin, a type of enterotoxin that affects intestinal cells. Pathogenic organisms in the O1 sero-group have caused the majority of cholera outbreaks and are subdivided into two biotypes: classical and El Tor. These two biotypes each contain two serotypes, called Inaba and Ogawa (some classifications recognize a third serotype, Hikojima), which are differentiated based on their biochemical properties, namely their expression of type-specific antigens.

Inaba and Ogawa serotypes both express a common cholera antigen known simply as A; however, only Ogawa expresses cholera antigen B and only Inaba expresses cholera antigen C. The classical biotype was responsible for most, if not all, of the six great cholera pandemics that swept through the world in the 19th and early 20th centuries. The seventh pandemic, which began in the mid-20th century and continues today, is caused by the El Tor biotype. This biotype possesses two characteristics that are of great epidemiological significance (Kindersley, 2009).

First, it is a much harder organism than the classical biotype, and it can survive for long periods of time in aquatic environments. Second, many people infected with the El Tor biotype experience only mild symptoms or no symptoms at all. Seriously ill patients are highly effective transmitters of cholera, but persons with mild or no symptoms are more likely to travel, thereby

also playing a crucial role in the spread of the disease. As barriers to commerce and to personal travel disappear, the potential for diseases to be transmitted rapidly from one continent to other increases (Kindersley, 2009).

Cholera is an intestinal disease that is the archetype of waterborne illnesses. It spreads by the faecal-oral route: infection spreads through a population when faeces containing the bacterium contaminate water that is then ingested by individuals. Transmission of the disease can also occur with food that has been irrigated, washed, or cooked with contaminated water. Foods that have the greatest potential to transmit the disease include shellfish and sea foods, especially if eaten raw; fruits and vegetables grown in soil that has been either fertilized with human excrement (night soil) or irrigated with raw sewage, and foods packed in contaminated ice (Farmer, 2016).

Once the bacterium infects the intestine, it secretes the enterotoxin from its external coating. The enterotoxin binds to a receptor on the cells of the lining of the small intestine. Part of the toxin then enters the intestinal cells. The toxin increases the activity of an enzyme that regulates a cellular pumping mechanism that controls the movement of water and electrolytes between the intestine and the circulatory system. This pump effectively becomes locked in the “on” position, causing the outflow of enormous quantities of fluid up to one litre (about one quart) per hour into the intestinal tract. All of the clinical manifestations of cholera can be attributed to the extreme loss of water and salts (Farmer, 2016).

2.2 Description and Characteristics of *Vibrio cholera*

Vibrio cholera, a curved Gram-negative bacillus belongs to the family, *Vibrionaceae* and shares some characteristics with the family, *Enterobacteriaceae*. The species *V. cholera*

comprises both pathogenic and non-pathogenic strains. *Vibrio cholera* O1 and O139 are the only serotypes responsible for the disease defined clinically and epidemiologically as cholera. *Vibrio cholera* O1 is divided into classical and El Tor biotypes, and into three serosubtypes - *Ogawa*, *Inaba*, and *Hikojima*. *Vibrio cholera* O139 has characteristics in common with the El Tor biotype but differs from O1 in its *polysaccharide* surface antigen. (Harris, 2017).

Cholera cases are confirmed through the isolation of *Vibrio cholera* O1 or O139 from stools in any patient with diarrhoea. Other serovars of *V. cholera* are generally termed non-O1, non-O139 strains. They are non-cholera genic, usually cause a milder form of gastroenteritis than O1 and O139, and are normally associated with sporadic cases and small outbreaks rather than with epidemics and pandemics (Harris, 2007).

Vibrio cholerae O1 Eltor is the commonest strain in Nigeria. About 75% of people infected with *V. cholera* do not develop any symptoms, although the bacteria are present in their faeces for 7-14 days after infection and are shed back into the environment, potentially infecting other people. Among people who develop symptoms, 80% have mild or moderate symptoms, while around 20% develop acute watery diarrhoea with severe dehydration. In severe infections, more than one quart of water and salts is lost per hour. The stool looks grey and has flecks of mucus in it- termed “rice-water stools”. Within hours, dehydration can become severe, causing intense thirst, muscle cramps, and weakness (Nelson, 2011).

Very little urine is produced and the eyes may become sunken, and the skin on the fingers may become much wrinkled. If dehydration is not treated, loss of water and salts can lead to kidney failure, shock, coma, and death. In people who survive, symptoms usually subside in 3 to 6

days. Most people are free of the bacteria in two weeks. The bacteria remain in a few people indefinitely without causing symptoms (Nelson, 2011).

The most important virulence factor associated with *V. cholera* O1 and O139 is the cholera toxin (ctx). The ctx genes (ctxA and ctxB) encoding the production of the cholera toxin have been sequenced and these have enabled the development of deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) probes and polymerase chain reaction (PCR) methods for the detection of the organism. In addition to cholera toxin, cholera genic strains of *V. cholera* possess the ability to adhere to, and colonise, the small intestine (colonisation factor), which has been ascribed to a toxin co-regulated pilus (TCP). Genes encoding major virulence-associated factors are found in clusters. It has been shown that ctx genes form part of a filamentous bacteriophage designated CTX phage. The pilus colonisation factor is also known to act as a receptor for the CTX phage and is encoded by the tcpA gene that is part of the *V. cholera* pathogenicity island (Sharman *et al*, 2011).

A complex cascade of regulatory proteins that control the expression of *V. cholera* virulence determinants has been reported. For instance, in responding to the chemical environment at the intestinal wall, the organism produces the TcpP/TcpH proteins, which, together with the ToxR/ToxS proteins, activate the expression of the ToxT regulatory protein. ToxT then directly activates the expression of virulence genes that produce the toxins, causing diarrhoea in the infected person and allowing the bacteria to colonise the intestine. Although reports on characteristics of Nigerian strains are insufficient implied that *Vibrio cholerae* from bi-weekly surveillance cultures for eight months were concordant with strains analysed at the onset of their study. It may therefore be assumed that the pathogenic potential and characteristics of *Vibrio cholerae* in Nigeria are similar to those that have been studied elsewhere (Nelson, 2011).

2.3 Factors Contributing to the Spread and Transmission of Cholera

The bacteria that causes cholera is usually passed out of the body of an infected person via the faeces. These bacteria may then contaminate a common source of drinking water and become widespread among populations. Poor water hygiene and sanitation are therefore important factors in the spread of the disease (Ryan, 2014).

Cholera has been almost eradicated in most developed nations worldwide. It is, however, still a major health hazard in sub-Saharan Africa, south and south-east Asia, some parts of the Middle East and South America. Outbreaks of cholera may occur after natural disasters such as earthquakes or after the war when there is overcrowding and a lack of sanitation, travellers are also susceptible to catching cholera, especially if they are travelling to areas where cholera is still endemic (Ryan, 2014).

For a cholera outbreak to occur, two conditions have to be met: there must be significant breaches in the water, sanitation, and hygiene infrastructure used by groups of people, permitting large-scale exposure to food or water contaminated with *Vibrio cholera* organisms; and cholera must be present in the population. Cholera has been proven to be transmitted through the faecal-oral route via contaminated food, carriers of the infection and inadequate sanitary conditions of the environment. The principal mode of transmission however remains ingestion of contaminated water or food (Ryan, 2014).

In Nigeria, the 1996 cholera outbreak in Ibadan (Southwest) was attributed to contaminated potable water sources. Street vended water and not washing hands with soap before / eating food are possible reasons for the 1995-1996 cholera outbreaks in Kano state. Drinking water sold by water vendors was also connected with an increased risk of contracting the disease. In

Katsina, the outbreak of the disease was linked to faecal contamination of well water from sellers. The recent 2010 outbreak of cholera was speculated to be directly related to sanitation and water supply. The hand-dug wells and contaminated ponds being relied on by most of the Northern states as a source of drinking water was a major transmission route during the outbreak. Perhaps, these wells were shallow; uncovered and diarrhoea discharge from cholera patients could easily contaminate water supplies (Shittu, 2011).

Another factor that may greatly contribute to the risk of cholera transmission is population movement which enhances the spread of the infectious agent to others and different sites. For instance, all the surviving residents that fled a two-month outbreak in Kebbi state (North-North) became indices for subsequent infection in the north and southern part of a neighbouring state (Shittu, 2011).

Additional overcrowding increases the risk of contact with vomitus, excreta and contaminated water or food. Since early detection and containment of cases (isolation facilities) are paramount in reducing transmission, poor access to health services and poor diagnosis may become the major barrier to controlling the infection. Lack of safe water and poor sanitation are important risk factors. All these features have contributed greatly to cholera infections in Nigeria (Shittu, 2011).

Cholera is a severe diarrhoea disease that is deadly without treatment. It is caused by poor hygiene and sanitation systems. When humans ingest cholera bacteria, they may not become sick themselves, but they still pass the bacteria in their stool. When human faeces contaminate food or water supplies, both can serve as ideal breeding grounds for the cholera bacteria. Because more than a million cholera bacteria approximately the amount you will find in a glass

of contaminated water are needed to cause illness, cholera usually isn't transmitted through casual person-to-person contact (World Health Organization, 2008). Some of the factors that contribute to the spread of Cholera includes;

Poor Sanitation

Cholera is more common where there is poor sanitation. Odimayo (2017) opined that cholera bacteria enter the body through the mouth, often in food or water that has been contaminated with human waste, due to poor sanitation and hygiene. They can also enter by eating seafood that is raw or not completely cooked, in particular shellfish native to estuary environments, such as oysters or crabs. Poorly cleaned vegetables irrigated by contaminated water sources are another common source of infection. Flush toilets also require the availability of water which was often cut therefore leading to unhygienic conditions or resorting to open defecation (Odimayo, 2017).

Contaminated Water

Contaminated water sources such as rivers, shallow wells and other unprotected water sources have high chances of faecal contamination. This is so especially in the rainy season when there is runoff and faeces get into water sources. The faeces are a result of open defecation by humans due to inadequate sanitation. Leaking sewage pipes have also led to faecal contamination of water sources. Surface water, which seeps into the porous ground and shallow wells become contaminated with faecal waste because of leaking sewerage pipes (Chipare, 2010). Piped water had become unreliable in many suburbs that people resorted to unimproved sources such as shallow wells. For instance as reported by the city of Harare (2008), challenges in procurement of chemicals and power outages resulted in erratic water supplies to residents who dug shallow unprotected wells which resulted in an explosive cholera epidemic. People dug

shallow wells as a way of coping with water shortages (Chipare 2010). The citing of the shallow wells could have contributed to cross-contamination where the wells were dug in close proximity to sewer systems.

Contaminated Food

Food can be a source of cholera infection as well as water which gets contaminated at point of use by hands that are soiled with human faeces. Food can be contaminated during or after preparation. WHO (2009) indicated fish/seafood, fruits and vegetables particularly taken from contaminated water and eaten raw or insufficiently cooked as a source of cholera infection. Fruits and vegetables grown at or near ground level, irrigated with water containing human waste, or "freshened" with contaminated water, and eaten raw are also sources of cholera infection. The survival and growth of *Vibrio cholerae* in foods depend on the physio-chemical properties of the particular foodstuff that has been contaminated. Food characteristics, which enhance the growth of *Vibrio cholerae*, are low temperature, high-organic content, neutral or alkaline pH, high-moisture content, and absence of other competing micro-organisms in the food (Odimayo, 2017).

Vibrio cholerae are very sensitive to heat and are rapidly killed when exposed to a temperature of 100°C. Drying and exposure to sunlight is also an effective means of killing *V. cholera* (WHO, 2009).

Domestic freezing is usually ineffective in sterilizing foods, and the organisms can survive for a long period in a frozen state.

Fruits and vegetables: In many countries, the practice of fertilizing gardens with untreated night soil and the habit of consuming uncooked vegetables have often resulted in cholera outbreaks. Vegetables may be contaminated during washing with polluted water. This can also

occur when contaminated water is injected into fruits, such as watermelons, to preserve their weight and taste. The pH of a specific fruit is an important factor that influences contamination by *Vibrio cholerae*. Sour fruits, such as lemons and oranges, with lower pH do not support the growth of *Vibrio cholerae*, and, thus, do not pose a risk of cholera transmission. Fruit pulp and concentrate preserved in cans are also less likely to be contaminated if they have an acidic pH. Spices, including raw onions and garlic, can support the survival of *Vibrio cholerae* for 2 to 3 days at ambient temperature (Odimayo, 2017).

Seafoods: The importance of fish and shellfish as a vehicle of transmission of cholera has been recognized by early observers. Fishes are likely to be contaminated by *Vibrio cholerae* when the surrounding water is contaminated by sewage or other environmental sources of *Vibrio cholerae* O1. It has been shown that *V. cholera* can survive in seawater in association with zooplankton (copepods). Zooplankton secretes a self-protective coat of chitin that can be dissolved by chitinase, an enzyme produced by *Vibrio cholerae* O1. Seafoods, including molluscs, crustaceans, crabs, and oysters, feed on plankton and can become infected with *Vibrio cholerae*. Once infected, particularly clams and oysters can harbour *Vibrio cholerae* for weeks, even if refrigerated. In crabs, the organisms can rapidly multiply at ambient temperature, and boiling for less than 10 minutes or steaming for less than 30 minutes does not completely kill *Vibrio cholerae* (Odimayo, 2017).

Dairy products: *Vibrio cholerae* O1 can survive for more than two weeks in different dairy products, including milk, milk products, soft deserts, and cakes. The addition of sugar and eggs enhances bacterial survival. Although *Vibrio cholerae* is killed by pasteurization of milk, the organisms can persist in raw milk for as long as four weeks, even if refrigerated.

Poultry and meat: Contamination of meat of animal origin occurs exogenously during processing, cooking, storage, or consumption. It has been shown that *Vibrio cholerae* can live and grow on cooked chicken, an increase in numbers of *Vibrio cholerae* from 10³ to 10⁶ within 16 hours has been demonstrated. An early observation by Seligmann indicates that consumption of improperly cooked horsemeat was incriminated in small outbreak of cholera. The meat had been prepared by an infected butcher who succumbed to cholera the next day. There are many other types of food that may be contaminated with *Vibrio cholerae*. *Vibrio cholerae* can survive on cooked rice, potatoes, eggs, and pasta for up to 5 days, and can also survive in spices, including pepper and cinnamon, for up to several days.

2.4 Symptoms of Cholera

Symptoms of cholera can begin as soon as a few hours or as long as five days after infection. Often, symptoms are mild. But sometimes they are very serious. About one in 20 people infected have severe watery diarrhoea accompanied by vomiting, which can quickly lead to dehydration. Although many infected people may have minimal or no symptoms, they can still contribute to the spread of the infection. Usually, one to five days after infection, and are the result of a toxin produced by the *Vibrio cholerae* bacterium that compels profuse amounts of fluid from the blood supply into the small and large intestines. An untreated cholera patient may produce several gallons of diarrhoeal fluid a day. Due to this rapid loss of fluids, severe dehydration and shock can occur in these individuals. Shock occurs due to the collapse of the circulatory system and if the fluid is not replaced, the patient may die within several hours (Kindersley, 2009)

Cholera is marked by the sudden onset of profuse, watery diarrhoea, typically after an incubation period of 12 to 28 hours. The fluid stools, commonly referred to as “rice water” stools, often contain flecks of mucus. The diarrhoea is frequently accompanied by vomiting,

and the patient rapidly becomes dehydrated. The patient is very thirsty and has a dry tongue. The blood pressure falls, the pulse becomes faint, and muscular cramps may become severe. The patient's eyes become hollow and sunken, and the skin becomes wrinkled, giving the hands the appearance of "washerwoman's hands." Children may also experience fever, lethargy, and seizures as a result of the extreme dehydration. The disease ordinarily runs its course in two to seven days.

The rapid loss of fluid from the bowel can, if untreated, lead to death—sometimes within hours—in more than 50 percent of those stricken. However, with proper modern treatment, mortality can essentially be prevented, with rates kept to less than 1 percent of those requiring therapy. This treatment consists largely of replacing lost fluid and salts with the oral or intravenous administration of an alkaline solution of sodium chloride. For oral rehydration the solution is made by using oral rehydration salts (ORS)—a measured mixture of glucose, sodium chloride, potassium chloride, and trisodium citrate. The mixture can be prepackaged and administered by nonmedical personnel, allowing cholera to be treated even under the most adverse conditions. ORS can generally be used to treat all but the most severely dehydrated patients, who require intravenous rehydration.

The administration of antibiotics such as tetracycline during the first day of treatment usually shortens the period of diarrhoea and decreases the amount of fluid replacement required. It is also important for patients to resume eating as soon as they are able in order to avoid malnutrition or to prevent existing malnutrition from becoming worse.

According to Diamond, M. (2009) the primary symptoms of cholera are:

Profuse diarrhoea sometimes called "rice-water stools"

Abdominal pain

Vomiting

Leg cramps

Low blood pressure

Thirst

Muscle cramps

2.5 Diagnosis of Cholera

In epidemic situations, a clinical diagnosis is made by taking a history of symptoms from the patient and by a brief examination only. People must begin treatment even before diagnostic work-up confirmation by laboratory analysis of specimens.

Lab tests include stool gram stain (gram-negative rods) culture, darkfield microscopy or stool PCR. Stool and swab samples collected in the acute stage of the disease, before antibiotics have been administered, are the most useful specimens for laboratory diagnosis (Laboratory Methods for the Diagnosis of Epidemic Dysentery and Cholera, 2003).

2.6 Prevention of Cholera

A safe and clean supply of water is the key to cholera prevention. Adequate chlorination of public water supplies and, in some cases, the distribution of chlorine tablets to households with instructions for their proper use are often effective measures. If chemical disinfection is not possible, people can be instructed to boil water before drinking it, but this may be difficult to accomplish, especially in poor countries where fuel may be expensive or unavailable (Opajobi, 2016).

Sometimes even simpler methods can be effective. For example, in Nigeria, where it is common for people to store water at home, cholera transmission was substantially reduced by replacing open containers, which allowed water to become easily contaminated, with narrow-necked jugs (Opajobi, 2016).

Methods have been developed to test and monitor environmental water supplies for the presence of *Vibrio cholerae*. Such methods are generally based on the detection of bacterial nucleic acids or on the use of antibodies specific to proteins on the surface of *Vibrio cholerae* cells. Rapid detection using such methods can facilitate the identification of possible sources of cholera outbreaks (Opajobi, 2016).

Another important intervention is the hygienic disposal of human waste. In areas lacking modern sewerage systems, the use of latrines can substantially lower the risk of infection. Ensuring the safety of food is yet another important control measure. During an epidemic of cholera, it is important that all food including leftovers be thoroughly cooked (to a core temperature of 70 °C [158 °F]) and that it be eaten before it cools. It is also important that stored food be covered to avoid contamination and that people always wash their hands after defecation and prior to food preparation. Foods sold by street vendors have been repeatedly implicated as sources of infection and should therefore be avoided by travellers to areas where cholera is endemic (Kindersley, 2009).

Vaccines have been developed against cholera, but they have not been considered effective for the prevention of cholera in large populations or during epidemics. Their usefulness is generally restricted to providing short-term protection for travellers visiting areas where cholera is endemic. Public health officials in some countries do not recommend cholera vaccination for any reason. Restrictions on travel and on food imports are among the measures that have at times been perceived as important for the prevention of cholera but have been shown to have relatively little benefit (Veres, 2007).

2.7 Cholera Treatment and Control Measures

In Nigeria, existing prevention and control strategies are multi-sectorial. Epidemic Preparedness and Response (EPR) approaches including registration of cases, case management and public health measures targeting personal hygiene and water treatment as well as emergency responses from both governmental and non-government agencies have contributed to the reduction in case of fatality rates over the years and should be sustained. Nevertheless, the need to explore more viable approaches cannot be overplayed if the infection has to be wholly curtailed (Kindersley, 2009).

Various studies elsewhere have utilized geographic and mathematical information systems to assess the spatial distribution of cholera at local levels, demonstrating case clustering and disease risk areas. Modelling techniques using climate data, remote monitoring, and geographic information systems also provide new techniques that may contribute to the prediction of cholera epidemics. We propose that such models can aid the understanding of epidemic processes and help design effective control strategies. Due to its endemicity in Nigeria, surveillance systems can provide early alerts to outbreaks, therefore leading to a coordinated response (Kindersley, 2009).

More importantly, it is necessary to introduce intervention measures that address the root problems of poor sanitation and unsafe water supplies in order to prevent future cholera epidemics. In this regard, perhaps, prevention of the disease is the best way to counter subsequent outbreaks. Simple measures as boiling the water for drinking, washing and cooking purposes, treatment of infected facilities, sewage and drainage systems, proper disposal of infected materials such as waste products, clothing, and beddings, treatment of infected faecal waste water produced by cholera victims and sterilisation of utensils either by boiling or by

using chlorine bleach. Studies have also indicated that the use of soap and hand-washing promotion can achieve a 26% to 62% decrease in the incidence of diarrhoea in developing countries (Hartwell and Veres, 2014).

Understanding the seasonality and location of outbreaks may also guide improving cholera control activities for vulnerable areas. Vigorous health promotion activities in terms of continuous public enlightenment on cholera are essential to controlling the infection. Health systems need to be strengthened with the provision of adequate manpower, equipment, drugs and consumables. There should also be an improvement in surveillance systems, communication and transport. Mechanisms for quick intervention should be put in place (Opajobi, 2016).

Defining strain diversity using molecular biology techniques may also assist with describing the intrinsic characteristics of diseases, such as the persistence of infection. The knowledge of the interaction of strain variants may also be a critical option for controlling the infection since molecular biology techniques are accessible. This can improve prevention plans, as well as risk assessment for potential cholera outbreaks (Hartwell and Veres, 2012).

Above all, World Health Organization (WHO) recommends that immunization with currently available cholera vaccines be used in conjunction with the usually recommended control measures in areas where cholera is endemic as well as in areas at risk of outbreaks. The oral vaccine has been shown to provide short-term protection of 85-90% against *V. cholera* O1 among all age groups at 4-6 months following immunization with minimal side effects. Although there is a vaccine against cholera, the CDC and World Health Organization don't normally recommend it, because it may not protect up to half of the people who receive it and

it lasts only a few months. However, you can protect yourself and your family by using only water that has been boiled, water that has been chemically disinfected or bottled water. Be sure to use bottled, boiled, or chemically disinfected water. (Hartwell and Veres, 2004).

CHAPTER THREE

3.0 MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 Introduction

Cholera seems to remain a major public health issue and it seems that inadequate provision of clean water, a clean environment and decent toilets contributed to its high prevalence in Nigeria, especially in Katsina State. The high morbidity and mortality associated with cholera produce grief and permanent anxiety to the family, pain, frustration and a poor quality of life to the patient, serious financial stress to the family and a large drain on the national health expenditure. In order to reduce high morbidity and mortality associated with this disease, there is a need to intensify effort towards educating the general populace on the factors contributing to the spread of cholera, causes, symptoms and preventable measure to this epidemic.

This chapter presents methodological aspects. It presents the target population, the techniques used in sampling selection, data collection and data analysis. It also discusses the administrative formalities that enabled the researcher to access data and the units of analysis and identification on the ground. The approach also presents the analytical strategies for data collection and research ethics.

3.1 Study Area

The study was conducted in Katsina Local Government Area of Katsina State in November, 2021. Katsina is a Local Government Area and the state capital of Katsina State in northern Nigeria. Katsina is located 260 kilometres (160 mi) east of the city of Sokoto and 135 kilometres (84 mi) northwest of Kano, close to the border with the Niger Republic. In 2016, Katsina's estimated population was 429,000 (NPC, 2006).

The city is the centre of an agricultural region production of groundnuts, cotton, hides, millet and guinea corn and also has mills for producing peanut oil and steel, it was also a centre for

large scale poultry farming of cows, goats, sheep and chickens. The city has a large Muslim population mainly from the Hausa and Fulani ethnics group.

Former Nigerian late President Umaru Yar'Adua was a nobleman of Katsina. The incumbent Governor of Katsina State is Aminu Bello Masari, who was sworn in as the executive Governor of the State on the 29th of May 2015, who had succeeded Barrister Ibrahim Shema.

Surrounded by a city wall 21 kilometres (13 mi) in length, Katsina is believed to have been founded circa 1100. In pre-Islamic times, Katsina's semi-divine ruler was known as the *Sarki*, who faced a summary death sentence if found to be ruling incompetently. From the 17th to the 18th century, Katsina was the commercial heart of Hausa land and became the largest of the seven Hausa city-states. Katsina was conquered by the Fulani during the Fulani War in 1807. In 1903, the Emir, Abubakar dan Ibrahim, accepted British rule, which continued until Nigerian independence from Britain in 1960.

During sub-Saharan trade, the city of Katsina was known to be one of the most vibrant and strong commercial centres, and was believed to be the strongest with the Hausa kingdoms in terms of commerce, trade and craft. The German explorer Friedrich Hornemann reached Katsina, the first Westerner to do so, at the beginning of the 19th century.

The city's history of western-style education dates back to the early 1950s, when the first middle school in northern Nigeria was established. There are now several institutions of higher learning, including two universities: Umaru Musa Yar'adua University and the private Katsina University. The city of Katsina is also home to a famous 18th-century mosque featuring the Gobarau Minaret, a 15-metre (50 ft) tower made from mud and palm branches.

Modern Katsina is a major collecting point for peanuts (groundnuts) and for hides and skins that are sent to Kano (92 miles [148 km] southeast) for export by road and rail. In Katsina's central market, sorghum, millet, onions and other vegetables, peanuts, indigo, goats, poultry, sheep, cattle, and cotton are traded. Traditional crafts of the town's predominantly Hausa population include weaving and dyeing cotton, working in leather and metal, and the design of pottery, embroidery, and calabashes. Modern industries were introduced in the 1970s and include vegetable oil mills and a steel-rolling plant.

Katsina Local Government Area is characterized by an almost all year round rainfall of 3,000–4,000 mm annually and maximum and minimum relative humidity of 90%–100% and 21%–23%, respectively, thereby making the vegetation an evergreen one. It is also made up of mangrove and lowland rainforests.

Fig 1: Map of Katsina Local Government Area

Source: Google Map 2021

3.2 Research Design

According to Binta (2004) research design is the process of measuring investigation aimed at identifying variables and their relationships with one another. It is used for the purpose of obtaining data to enable the researcher to test the hypothesis. Ahmad (2011), defined research design as an outline or scheme that serves as a useful guide to the researcher in his effort to generate data for the research.

This study adopted experimental, laboratory-based study and descriptive research design of survey type. The descriptive research design allows the researcher to use a subset of a population as a sample (Nworgu, 2006). It also, allows the use of a questionnaire for the collection of data from respondents and attempts to describe all aspects of respondents' perception and/or opinion (Nwanna, 2000). The rationales behind this design were many. Firstly, Katsina Local Government Area is wide and the population is scattered on the rough terrains. A survey designer made use of a questionnaire for the collection of information from the fractional part of the entire population. Data gathered from the representative sample could be generalized to the entire population.

3.3 Population of the Study

A research population refers to the group of people or objects on which the researcher would like the results of his findings to be generalized. (Osuala, 2005).

Population according to Hassan (2004), refers to the aggregate number of elements or observations considered for the research work from which sample is selected.

The target population of this study comprised of patients hospitalised for treatment of cholera at the General Hospital Katsina.

3.4 Sample and Sampling Technique

Sample size simply means the part proportion of the total population to represent the total population under study. The sampling technique on the other hand has to do with the technique or method employed in taking the sample size from the population.

A total number of 60 respondents from the targeted population will be selected for this study, the selection of the respondents was stratified so that intended respondents could be selected. However only cholera patients hospitalised were selected so that they can be able to answer

the questions appropriately, simple random sampling technique was used for the selection of the respondents. Hat-Replacement – pick method was used in order to give everyone equal chances of being selected like other ones.

3.5 Instrument for Data Collection

A questionnaire was used to get detailed and valid information on the chosen topic; the questionnaire's items are carefully designed to elicit objective responses to the research questions postulated in Chapter One. The type of questions used consists of structured questions (or fixed responses) where the respondents are restricted to some response option that best suited his/her feeling. The respondents were to read the items and tick the appropriate columns.

3.6 Reliability and validity of the instrument for data collection

Reliability and validity are important aspects of selecting a survey instrument. Reliability refers to the extent that the instrument yields the same results over multiple trials. Validity refers to the extent that the instrument measures what it was designed to measure.

To ensure content validation, a draft questionnaire will be submitted to the supervisor prior to fieldwork (administration) for content validation, to ensure that the items were clear and that appropriate language and expressions have been used, and his suggestion and the recommendation will be taken into consideration in the final draft of the instrument.

3.7 Method of Data Collection

Primary and secondary data was the main source of data for this study. The type of data, their sources and the instruments used in gathering them are discussed as follows:

Primary data was collected through a well-structured questionnaire. The questionnaires were structured into two sections. The first section focused on the demographic characteristics of respondents and the second section looked at the effect of advertising on sales of consumer goods.

The type of questions used consists of a structured questionnaire (or fixed response) where the respondents are restricted to some response option that best suited his/her feeling. 15 questions were asked to gather enough information regarding the subject matter. The researcher was to read the questions to the respondents and guide them on how to tick the appropriate columns. As depicted in the instructions at the beginning of the section, the questionnaires were distributed to the respondents, the items of the questionnaires were read to the respondents carefully until the researcher make sure that they understand the items, and later they were instructed on how to fill them appropriately. All the completed questionnaires will be collected personally by the researcher. That is, there will be a 100% return rate.

The secondary data was obtained from articles, journals and publishes annual reports. Saunders et al (2007) quote Stewart and Kamins (1993) as stating that secondary data are likely to be of higher quality than could be obtained by collecting empirical data.

3.8 Method of Data Analysis

The study uses descriptive statistical methods (tables and simple percentages) to represent the responses from the questionnaires administered. The researcher used a simple percentage for analyzing the data collected for this research work. Data was presented by using tables. Presentation of the data with these statistical tools will make the analysis very easy. However, the researcher uses ANOVA analysis to test the hypotheses at the alpha level of 0.05, if the P-value is ($P < 0.05$) or $F > F_{crit}$, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative

hypothesis, while if P-value ($P \geq 0.05$) and $F < F_{crit}$, we reject the alternative hypothesis and accept the null hypotheses.

The researcher used simple percentages in computing the status of the respondent using the formula below;

$$\text{Percentage} = \frac{\text{number of responses}}{\text{total frequency}} = \times 100/1$$

3.9 Isolation and Identification of *Vibrio cholerae* from the faecal sample

Vibrio is short, curved, Gram-negative rods measuring $2 \times 0.5 \mu\text{m}$ and that is motile by its single polar flagellum.

It is a facultative anaerobe that produces acid from carbohydrate fermentation.

The growth of most species of *Vibrio* is facilitated by Na^+ ion but not for *Vibrio cholerae* and *Vibrio mimicus* as these both can grow well in absence of NaCl.

Vibrio produces enzymes like protease, nuclease, lipase, and chitinase.

Around 12 species of *Vibrio* are identified to cause gastrointestinal and extra gastrointestinal infections that include *V. cholerae*, *V. parahaemolyticus*, *V. vulnificus*, *V. mimicus*, and *V. alginolyticus*.

Vibrio cholerae (strain O1 and O139) is reported in the number of Cholera outbreak. It is non-halophilic that can grow in media without NaCl and fails to grow in media containing $>6\%$ NaCl.

The optimum temperature for its growth is 37°C and pH is 8.2.

3.9.1 Requirements

Thiosulfate citrate bile salts sucrose (TCBS) agar: Suspend the agar media in distilled water and heat to dissolve the media completely. Do not autoclave and pour the media into sterile plates.

Alkaline Peptone Water (APW): Measure 5 gm of peptone and 5 gm of NaCl and dissolve it in distilled water. Adjust the pH 8.6 to 9.0 using 1 mol/L sodium hydroxide. Dispense the medium in a 10 ml screw-cap tube and sterilize by autoclaving at 121°C for 15 minutes.

3.9.2 Laboratory Diagnosis of *Vibrio cholerae*

Specimen: The most required specimen for *Vibrio* spp. is a faecal matter. Rectal swabs are most accepted during the initial phase of the disease. The specimen should be collected in a sterile container and delivered as soon as possible to the microbiology lab. In the case of delay 5 ml, faeces can be added in 20 ml Transport medium like alkaline transport medium with boric acid or Cary-Blair medium.

Microscopy: Direct microscopy is not preferred.

Culture:

- Suspend 2 ml faeces in 20 ml Alkaline Peptone Water (APW) with pH-8.6 and then incubate APW at 37°C exactly for 5 hrs.
- Take loopful of the surface from APW and inoculate in Thiosulfate citrate bile salts sucrose (TCBS) agar and perform streaking on the agar surface. Incubate the plate at 37°C overnight.
- The next day examines the TCBS plate for *Vibrio* like colonies (Table 1). Pick up the yellow colony of *Vibrio* from TCBS and inoculate in Nutrient Agar (NA) without NaCl. Incubate the media at 37°C for 5 hours.

- After incubation observe the Nutrient Agar (NA) plate for the growth of the culture. *Vibrio cholerae* can grow with colourless, glistening, translucent colonies in Nutrient agar without NaCl. *Vibrio cholerae* should be confirmed by its sufficient growth on NA without salt, either on 1% tryptone water without NaCl or in a CLED plate. This conventional test is reliable enough for the isolation and identification of *Vibrio cholerae*. from other *Vibrio* sp.
- For further confirmation, perform Gram staining, Oxidase test, and Slide agglutination test. For this test, culture should always be taken from non-selective media like Nutrient agar. For slide agglutination tests take a small volume of culture from NA on a clean slide and make emulsion by adding saline water. Add an equal volume of antiserum O1 and tilt the slide back and forth for 30 sec-1 min. *Vibrio cholerae* produces strong clumping which is a positive test for slide agglutination. If the result is negative then perform the test again with antisera 0139.
- If Gram's staining report is a negative rod, the Oxidase test is positive and the Slide agglutination test is also positive then presents the Report to the physician as Cholera.

3.10 Summary of the Chapter

This chapter clearly outlines the methodology employed in achieving the objectives for this study. It covers the research design, target population, sample size, sampling technique, Reliability and validity of the instrument for data collection, data collection procedure and data analysis techniques and isolation and identification of *Vibro cholera*.

CHAPTER FOUR

4.0 Results

4.1 Responses to the Questionnaires

The data obtained from the returned questionnaires were tabulated as age, frequency and PERCENTAGE (%) as shown in table 4.1

Table 4.1: Age, Frequency and percentage of the respondents

Age	No of Respondents	Percentage%
01 – 20	29	48
21 - 40	23	38
41 - Above.	8	14
TOTAL	60	100

The above table depicts that 29 respondents represented 48% of the respondents are between the ranges of 01 – 20 years old, while 23 respondents represented 38% of the respondents fall within the range of 21 – 40 years of age. 8 respondents represented 14% of the respondents fall within the range of 41 years and above. Therefore, this depicts that, 01 – 20 years of age form the highest number of respondents.

Table 4.2: Gender, Frequency and Percentage of the respondents

Gender	No of Respondents	Percentage%
Male	26	43
Female	34	57
TOTAL	60	100

The above table depicts that 26 respondents are Males, which form the 43% of the total respondents, while 34 respondents represented 57% of the respondents are female. This means that there are more females than males among the respondents

Table 3: Contributing Factors

S/N	QUESTIONS	OPTIONS / NO OF RESPONDENTS				TOTAL
Q1	Source of drinking water supply	Tap / Borehole	Well	Stream	Others	
		16 (27%)	29 (48%)	13 (22%)	2 (3%)	60 (100%)
Q2	Type of latrine/toilet	Water Closet	Pit Latrine	Plastic Bag	Others	
		3 (5%)	53 (89%)	2 (3%)	2 (3%)	60 (100%)
Q3	Do you keep refuse around your House?	Yes	No	Sometimes	Not at all	
		36 (61%)	11 (18%)	11 (18%)	2 (3%)	60 (100%)
Q4	Do you drink untreated water	Yes	No	Sometimes	Not at all	
		24 (40%)	13 (22%)	16 (27%)	7 (11%)	60 (100%)
Q5	Do you eat food that has stayed for a long time after cooking?	Yes	No	Sometimes	Not at all	
		39 (66%)	4 (6%)	15 (25%)	2 (3%)	60 (100%)

S/N	QUESTIONS	OPTIONS / NO OF RESPONDENTS				TOTAL
Q1	Do you wash fruits before eating?	Yes 28 (47%)	No 2 (3%)	Sometimes 29 (48%)	Not at all 1 (2%)	60 (100%)
Q2	How often do you clean your toilet?	Daily 4 (6%)	Weekly 33 (56%)	Monthly 23 (38%)	Not all 0 (0)	60 (100%)
Q3	Do you wash your hands with soap after coming out from the toilet?	Yes 6 (10%)	No 11 (18%)	Sometimes 36 (60%)	Not at all 7 (12%)	60 (100%)
Q4	Do you wash your hands before and after eating food?	Yes 29 (48%)	No 3 (5%)	Sometimes 26 (44%)	Not at all 2 (3%)	60 (100%)
Q5	Do you observe regular sanitation around your House?	Yes 29 (48%)	No 5 (8%)	Sometimes 26 (44%)	Not at all 0 (0)	60 (100%)
Q6	Do you have access to proper sewage disposal?	Yes 16 (27%)	No 26 (43%)	Sometimes 7 (12%)	Not at all 11 (18%)	60 (100%)
Q7	Do you have access to clean water in your Community?	Yes 14 (23%)	No 11 (18%)	Sometimes 33 (56%)	Not at all 2 (3%)	60 (100%)
Q8	Are you aware with the mode and pattern of cholera transmission through various communication channels, such as television, radio, and social media?	Yes 3 (5%)	No 29 (49%)	Sometimes 11 (18%)	Not at all 17 (28%)	60 (100%)

Table 4: Preventive Measures

Q9	Did you visit cholera centre to receive treatment immediately after being infected?	Yes 9 (15%)	No 43 (72%)	Sometimes 3 (5%)	Not at all 5 (8 %)	60 (100%)
Q10	Is there an availability to access a health care centre for those who are infected?	Yes 48 (80%)	No 2 (3%)	Sometimes 7 (12%)	Not at all 3 (5%)	60 (100%)

Table 5. Identified *Vibrio* spp.

Species	Colonies in TCBS	Growth in 0.0% NaCl	Gram's test	Oxidase	Indole
<i>V. cholerae</i>	Yellow	+	-	+	+
<i>V. mimicus</i>	Green	+	-	+	+

CHAPTER FIVE

5.0 DISCUSSION, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Discussion

Cholera is an acute, diarrheal illness caused by infection of the intestine with the bacterium *Vibrio cholerae*. It was first identified in Bangladesh in 1992, the infection is often mild or without symptoms, but sometimes can be severe. When humans ingest cholera bacteria, they may not become sick themselves, but they still pass the bacteria in their stool. When human faeces contaminate food or water supplies, both can serve as ideal breeding grounds for the cholera bacteria. Cholera usually isn't transmitted through casual person-to-person contact. The disease is transmitted through waterborne and foodborne transmission.

Based on the contributing factors, the result of the study shows that; 16 respondents represented 27% of the respondents use Tap / Borehole as a source of water supply, 29 respondents represented 48% of the respondents use well as a source of water supply while 13 respondents represented 22% of the respondents use stream water as their source of water supply.

It also depicts that 36 respondents represented 61% of the respondents used to keep refuse around their houses, while 11 respondents represented 18% of the respondents and 2 respondents represented 3% indicated they don't keep refuse around their houses and 11 respondents represented 18% of the respondents indicated that sometimes they keep it around their houses, but not all the time.

It was also revealed that 14 respondents represented 23% of the respondents have access to clean water in their Community, while 11 respondents represented 18% of the respondents and 2 respondents represented 3% of the respondents implied that they don't have access to clean

water in their community, and 33 respondents represented 56% of the respondents indicated that sometimes they have access to clean water in their community, but not all the time.

The result further shows that 39 respondents represented 66% of the respondents indicated that they used to eat food that has stayed for a long time after cooking, while 4 respondents represented 6% of the respondents and 2 respondents represented 3% of the respondents implied that they don't eat food that has stayed for a long time after cooking, and 15 respondents represented 25% of the respondents indicated that sometimes they eat food that has stayed for a long time after cooking, but not all the time.

Based on the preventive measures; the result shows that only 28 respondents represented 47% of the respondents wash fruits before eating, while 2 respondents represented 3% of the respondents and another 1 respondent opined that they don't wash fruits before eating. 29 respondents represented 48% of the respondents indicated that sometimes they wash fruits before eating but not all the time. It was also revealed that 9 respondents represented 15% of the respondents indicated that they visit cholera centre to receive treatment immediately after being infected, while 43 respondents represented 72% of the respondents and 5 respondents represented 8% of the respondents implied that they did not visit cholera centre to receive treatment immediately after been infected, and 3 respondents represented 5% of the respondents indicated that sometimes they visit cholera centre to receive treatment immediately after been infected, but sometimes they stayed at home trying different types of cholera medication before visiting the cholera centre.

The result further depicts that only 6 respondents represented 10% of the respondents wash their hands with soap after coming out from the toilet, while 11 respondents represented 18% of the respondents and 7 respondents represented 12% indicated they don't wash their hands with soap after coming out from the toilet, whereas 36 respondents represented 60% of the

respondents opined they only wash their hands with soap after coming out from the toilet once in a while.

The result further revealed that only 29 respondents represented 48% of the respondents wash their hands before and after eating food, while 3 respondents represented 5% of the respondents and 2 respondents represented 3% indicated they don't wash their hands before and after eating food and 26 respondents represented 44% of the respondents indicated that sometimes they wash their hand before and after eating food, but not all the time.

It further shows that only 4 respondents represented 6% of the respondents used to clean their toilet daily, while 33 respondents represented 56% of the respondents opined that they use to clean their toilets weekly and 23 respondents represented 38% of the respondents indicate that they use to clean their toiler once in a month or in 2 to 3 month.

Also, two gram-negative *Vibrio* spp were identified from the isolation, which is; *V. cholera*, *V. mimicus*.

Based on what have been discovered from the research findings, cholera can be transmitted through waterborne transmission once someone consumes water that is contaminated with faeces from an infected person. This is common in areas with poor sewage systems and unclean drinking water. Also, consumption of cholera can be through drinking contaminated water or eating foods that have been washed with or made with contaminated water. Transmission may also occur when an individual eats raw or undercooked shellfish. Any infected water and any foods washed in the water, as well as shellfish living in the affected waterway, can cause an infection. Raw, unpeeled fruits and vegetables are also frequent sources of cholera infection in areas where cholera is endemic.

5.2 Conclusion

The deadly disease called cholera is caused by eating contaminated food and water. The primary cause of this syndrome is an enterotoxin. (Cholera toxin). Cholera is an acute secretory diarrheal illness caused by toxin producing strains of the Gram-negative bacterium *Vibrio cholera*. Severe cholera is characterized by profound fluid and electrolyte losses in the stool and the rapid development of hypovolemic shock, often within 24 h from the initial onset of vomiting and diarrhoea.

In stool specimens, *V. cholerae* can be easily identified by its characteristic yellow colonies. Physicians think that vibrio only grows in association with salt water and in most cases cholera can be successfully treated with oral rehydration therapy, which is highly effective. An effective and relatively cheap method to prevent the transmission of cholera is to drink purified water and uncontaminated food.

5.3 Recommendations

- Do not buy food from unlicensed food premises or illegal hawkers; Pay attention to hygienic condition of shops and the holding temperature of food.
- Keep raw and cooked food separately. Defrost foods only when needed; Use separate utensils and equipment to handle raw food and cooked food to prevent cross contamination
- Consume cooked food as soon as possible; Left-over food must be stored in a refrigerator at a temperature below 4 degrees Celsius and be reheated thoroughly before consumption.
- Discard any food if spoilage is suspected; and Boil water thoroughly before drinking.
- Wash hands thoroughly with soap, before eating, preparing food and after going to toilet.

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APPENDIX I QUESTIONNAIRE

Being a final year student of Alqalam University Katsina, I'm conducting a research on *factors contributing to the spread of cholera in Katsina metropolis*. Please kindly tick or fill as appropriate option of your choice from the following questions.

SECTION (A): Personal Information

1. Age of the respondent: 1 – 20 years () 21 – 40 () 41 and above ()
2. Sex of the respondent: Male () Female ()

SECTION (B): Tick in the Appropriate Boxes.

Q1. Source of drinking water supply.

- a. Tap/Borehole () b. Well () c. Stream () d. Others ()

Q2. Type of latrine/toilet

- a. Water Closet () b. Pit latrine () c. Plastic Bag/ Bucket () d. Others ()

Q3. How often do you clean your toilet?

- a. Daily () b. Weekly () c. Monthly () d. Not at all ()

Q4. Do you wash your hands with soap after coming out from the toilet?

- a. Yes b. No c. Sometimes d. Not at all ()

Q5. Do you wash fruits before eating?

- a. Yes b. No c. Sometimes d. Not at all ()

Q6. Do you wash your hands before and after eating food?

- a. Yes b. No c. Sometimes d. Not at all ()

Q7. Do you keep refuse around your House?

- a. Yes b. No c. Sometimes d. Not at all ()

Q8. Do you observe regular sanitation around your House?

- a. Yes b. No c. Sometimes d. Not at all ()

Q9. Do you eat food in untidy and unclean environment?

- a. Yes b. No c. Sometimes d. Not at all ()

Q10. Do you eat food that has stayed for a long time after cooking?

- a. Yes b. No c. Sometimes d. Not at all ()

Q11. Do you have access to proper sewage disposal?

- a. Yes b. No c. Sometimes d. Not at all ()

Q12. Do you have access to clean water in your Community?

- a. Yes b. No c. Sometimes d. Not at all ()

Q13. Are you aware with the mode and pattern of cholera transmission through various communication channels, such as television, radio, and social media?

- a. Yes b. No c. Sometimes d. Not at all ()

Q14. Did you visit cholera center to receive treatment immediately after been infected?

- a. Yes b. No c. Sometimes d. Not at all ()

Q15. Is there an availability to access a health care center for those who are infected ?

- a. Yes b. No c. Sometimes d. Not at all ()

APPENDIX II

Hypotheses Testing

The following are the hypotheses to be tested:

H0: There is no significant effects of poor sanitation, water contamination or food contamination as a factors contribute to the spread of Cholera in Katsina metropolis.

H1: There is a significant effects of poor sanitation, water contamination or food contamination as a factors contribute to the spread of Cholera in Katsina metropolis.

The research will use ANOVA analysis to test the hypotheses at alpha level of 0.05, if the P value is ($P < 0.05$) and $F > F$ crit, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis, while if P value isj ($P \geq 0.05$) and $F < F$ crit, we reject the alternative hypothesis and accept the null hypotheses.

Anova: Two-Factor
With Replication

Summary	No	Sometimes	Yes	Total		
Count	3	3	3	9		
Sum	39	42	99	180		
Average	13	14	33	20		
Variance	49	7	63	125		
Total						
Count	3	3	3			
Sum	39	42	99			
Average	13	14	33			
Variance	49	7	63			
Anova						
Source Of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Sample	0	0	65535	65535		
Columns	762	2	381	9.6050420	0.01348127	5.14325
				2	2	3
Interaction	0	0	65535	65535		
Within	238	6	39.666			
			67			
Total	1000	8				

The table above displays that P value is < 0.05 (P is 0.01) and $F > F_{crit}$, ($9.6 > 5.1$). Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected and the result was significant. This implies that there is a significant effects of poor sanitation, water contamination and food contamination as a factors contribute to the spread of Cholera in Katsina metropolis.